

Characterization of the Breast Lesions by Ultrasonoelastography and Comparison with FNAC Findings

Sreekanth Dakaraju. P¹, V. Shalini Reddy², Ramesh Vasudevan^{3*}

¹Professor, Department of Radiology, Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

²Professor, Department of Radiology, Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

³Professor, Department of General Surgery, Apollo Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Ramesh Vasudevan

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Abstract:

Introduction: Breast lesions are most prevalent cancer type among women globally that require early diagnosis for successful management and to avoid biopsies. Ultrasonography (USG), elastography and combined Ultrasono elastography are effective diagnostic modalities for characterization of breast lesions. This study was focused on characterization of the breast lesions by ultrasono elastography and comparison with FNAC findings. **Material and Methods:** Sixty women with palpable breast masses above 21 years were subjected to detailed clinical examination. Cases with palpable breast lesions to ultrasound imaging and elastography. The FNAC was performed to accurate the ultrasound findings.

Results: The combined diagnostic outcome of grey scale USG and elastography showed 100%, 95.65%, 94.28%, 100% and 97.48% of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic accuracy respectively.

Conclusion: The concurrent use of grey scale ultrasonography and elastography is advantageous in most cases for the enhanced characterization of palpable lesions, leading to a diagnosis with high accuracy. These imaging methods relieve patient anxiety and prevent unnecessary procedures in cases where the imaging results are definitively benign.

Keywords: Breast Lesions, Elastography, Ultrasonography, Diagnostic Accuracy.

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Introduction

Breast lesions account for the majority of newly diagnosed cancer cases, making them the most common cancer in women. In 2020, reports of new cases of breast lesions amounted to approximately 2.3 million, accounting for 11.7% of all cancer types. This figure could potentially increase to over 2 million cases by 2030. India is among the three countries that contribute one-third of the global breast cancer burden, along with China and the United States, where the incidence of the disease is rising quickly [4].

Breast cancer accounted for 10.6% of all cancer-related deaths in India and 13.5% of all cancer types, according to Globocan 2020 [5]. Many nations still widely employ fine-needle aspiration cytology to assess breast masses in both palpable and non-palpable lesions due to its fast, precise, and economical diagnosis (6). Non-invasive imaging techniques like ultrasound elastography, B-mode US, and mammography often detect breast lesions [7]. Elastography may improve breast

sonography's specificity in distinguishing benign from malignant masses, hence reducing the number of benign biopsies [8]. Combining ultrasonography and elastography enhances the specificity of screening by considering the hardness of the lesions. The colour and strain ratio are useful indicators for discriminating between benign and malignant tumors [9].

The strain ratio is an important statistic for characterizing lesions by comparing their relative compliance, stiffness, or deformability to that of healthy surrounding tissue. In view of this, the goal of this study was to compare the use of greyscale USG and ultrasono elastography in the characterization of breast lesions to FNAC findings.

Materials and Methods

Sixty women with palpable breast masses attending an outpatient clinic of general surgery referred to the department of radiology at the Apollo Institute

of Medical Sciences, Hyderabad, during March 2023 to June 2024 were recruited. We included participants with palpable breast lumps who were willing to participate, family history of breast lesions and consented to the FNAC procedure. Cases with pregnancy, lactation, recurrent breast cancers, inflammatory breast conditions, clinically diagnosed breast lesions, and not willing to participate were excluded. The institutional ethics committee approved the study protocol and obtained written informed consent from study participants.

We conducted detailed clinical and physical examinations on the participants and obtained a detailed history. We referred cases with palpable breast lesions to ultrasound imaging and

elastography. The FNAC was performed to accurate the ultrasound findings. We performed ultrasonography in a supine position to identify the lesion site, its distance from the nipple, and its side, then classified the identified lesions using BIRADS categories. Collected data was analysed using SPSS version 23.0. We represented categorical variables in frequency and percentages. We represented the continuous variable as mean and standard deviation. A chi-square test was used to compare the data, and $p < 0.05$ was considered a statistically significant outcome. We represented the overall outcome of ultrasonography and elastography in sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy.

Results

Table 1: Sociodemographic details of study participants.

Sociodemographic data	Total no of cases (n=60)	
	Frequency	Percentage
Age (In years)		
21-40	11	18.33%
41-60	39	65%
>60	10	16.67%
Laterality of lesion		
Unilateral right	25	41.67%
Unilateral left	28	46.67%
Bilateral	07	11.66%

Table 2: Identification lesion type by different diagnostic tools and method.

Diagnostic methods	Malignant	Benign
Strain ratio	39 (65%)	21 (35%)
Grey scale USG	38 (63.33%)	22 (36.67%)
Elastography	41 (68.33%)	19 (31.66%)
FNAC	37 (61.67%)	23 (38.33%)

Graph 1: Smart art showing distribution of cases by FNAC findings

Table 3: Breast lesion detection by different diagnostic methods.

Diagnostic outcome	FNAC	
	Malignant (n=37)	Benign (n=23)
Stain Ratio		
Malignant (n=39)	36	03
Benign (n=21)	01	20
Grey scale USG		
Malignant (n=38)	36	02
Benign (n=22)	01	21
Elastography		
Malignant (n=41)	37	04
Benign (n=19)	00	19

Graph 2: Combined diagnostic outcome of elastography and grey scale USG in breast lesions**Table 4: Comparison of diagnostic outcome of breast lesions between different methods.**

Outcome	Strain ratio	Grey scale USG	Elastography
Sensitivity	97.29%	97.29%	100%
Specificity	91.30%	91.30%	82.60%
PPV	92.30%	95.73%	90.24%
NPV	86.95%	95.45%	100%
Diagnostic accuracy	91.96%	94.92%	93.21%

Discussion

The majority of cases (65%) were between the ages of 41 and 60, followed by 21 to 40 (18.33%) and above 60 (16.67%). Unilateral left side lesions (46.67%) were most prevalent, followed by unilateral right side (41.67%) and bilateral lesions (11.66%) (Table 1). In 65% of cases, the strain ratio revealed malignant lesions, while benign lesions were found in 35%. The gray scale USG detected malignant lesions in 63.33% and 36.67% of patients, respectively. Elastography detected 68.33% of malignant lesions and 31.66% of benign lesions. In 61.67% of cases, the FNAC results revealed malignant lesions, while benign lesions

were found in 38.33% of cases. Most of the benign lesions were fibroadenomas (75.67%), then suppurative lesions (10.81%), ductal hyperplasia (5.40%), fibrocysts (5.40%), and benign cystic lesions (2.70%). Ductal carcinoma was the most prevalent malignant lesion in 56.52% of cases, followed by atypical ductal hyperplasia in 26.08%, ductal carcinoma in situ in 13.04%, and malignant phyllodes in 4.34% of cases (Table 2 & Graph 1).

The combined diagnostic outcome of grey scale USG and elastography showed 100%, 95.65%, 94.28%, 100% and 97.48% of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic accuracy respectively (Graph 2). When comparing the results

of strain ratio and FNAC findings, the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and diagnostic accuracy were 97.29%, 91.30%, 92.30%, 86.95%, and 91.96%, respectively. The grey scale USG comparison with the FNAC results indicated 97.29%, 91.30%, and 95.73%. Sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and diagnostic accuracy are 95.45% and 94.92%, respectively. When FNAC results were compared to elastography, the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and diagnostic accuracy were 100%, 82.60%, 90.24%, 100%, and 93.21%, respectively (Table 4).

A prospective cross-sectional study conducted by Tiwari P et al. assessed breast lesions using mammography and ultrasound with fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC). Determined sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value for mammography and ultrasound in the diagnosis of breast lesions as 77.77%, 97.72%, 87.5%, 95.55%, 55.55%, 97.72%, 83.33%, and 91.48%, respectively. The research indicated that the combination of mammography and ultrasound is more successful in detecting breast lesions, exhibiting superior sensitivity and negative predictive value [10]. Shetty MK et al. reported that mammography with USG are effective modalities in the diagnosis of benign and malignant breast lesion with 100% of sensitivity, 80.1% of specificity and 100% of negative predictive value [11].

Kumar AMS et al. evaluated 90 cases found out malignant lesions in 48.89% and benign lesions in 51.11% of cases. Determined sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy was 71.74%, 90.91% and 81.11% for B-mode USG; whereas for elastography, it was 95.65%, 68.18% and 82.22% respectively [12]. Thomas R et al., reported higher sensitivity for USG elastography (91.67%) compared to X-ray mammography (87.88%) and USG alone (90.91%). Combination three methods are effective in determining and management of lesion with comparable specificity with histopathological examination [13].

Chhadi S et al. reviewed 126 cases ultrasonographically diagnosed with breast lesions with conventional B-mode USG, elastography with FNAC correlation found out malignant lesions in 48.3% and benign in 51.7% of cases. Study reported that USG elastography can improve the sensitivity and specificity of USG and can minimize the unwanted biopsy rate [14]. Sakalecha AK et al., reported 89.8%, 96.15%, 95.65%, 90.91% and 93.07% of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and diagnostic accuracy. Strain ratio showed 100%, 98.11%, 97.96%, 100% and 99.01% of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and diagnostic accuracy.

Study also stated that whenever USG findings are equivocal, elastography findings may play vital role in characterizing the lesions [15]. Menezes R et al. evaluated diagnostic performance of USG, elastography in determining the breast lesion correlating with FNAC showed 100% and 82.66% of sensitivity and specificity respectively [16]. Bojanic K et al., reported sensitivity and specificity of 90.5% and 93.2% for elastography score and 87.5% and 87.6% for strain ratio.

Elastography alongside B-mode USG escalated the specificity, diagnostic accuracy and PPV [17]. The present findings are in accordance with above findings where grey scale USG and elastography has superior sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic accuracy.

Conclusion

The integrated diagnostic results of grey scale ultrasound and elastography demonstrated sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy of 100%, 95.65%, 94.28%, 100%, and 97.48%, respectively.

The concurrent use of grey scale ultrasonography and elastography is advantageous in most cases for the enhanced characterization of palpable lesions, leading to a diagnosis with high accuracy. These imaging methods relieve patient anxiety and prevent unnecessary procedures in cases where the imaging results are definitively benign.

References

1. Agarwal NK, Singh S, Patel P, et al. Demographics of breast cancer and non-malignant breast lesions in Western India: A study of 8000 breast pathologies. *Annals of Oncology*. 2022; 33(3): S187.
2. Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, Laversanne M, Soerjomataram I, Jemal A, Bray F. Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. *CA Cancer J Clin*. 2021; 71:209–249.
3. DeSantis C, Siegel R, Bandi P, Jemal A. Breast cancer statistics, 2011. *CA Cancer J Clin*. 2011; 61:409–418.
4. Malvia S, Bagadi SA, Dubey US, Saxena S: Epidemiology of breast cancer in Indian women. *Asia Pac J Clin Oncol* 2017; 13(4):289–295.
5. International Agency for Research on Cancer. India Source: Globocan 2020. [Cited 11 June 2021]. Available from: <https://gco.iarc.fr/today/data/factsheets/populations/356-india-fact-sheets.pdf>
6. Radhakrishna S, Gayathri A, Chegu D. Needle core biopsy for breast lesions: An audit of 467

- needle core biopsies. *Indian J Med Paediatr Oncol.* 2013; 34:252-256
7. Elkhartbotly A, Farouk HM. Ultrasound elastography improves differentiation between benign and malignant breast lumps using B-mode ultrasound and color Doppler. *Egyptian J Radiol Nuclear Med.* 2015; 46:1231–1239.
 8. Lee JH, Kim SH, Kang BJ, Choi JJ, Jeong SH, Yim HW, Song BJ. Role and clinical usefulness of elastography in small breast masses. *Acad Radiol.* 2011; 18:74–80.
 9. Moss HA, Britton PD, Flower CD, Freeman AH, Lomas DJ, Warren RM. How reliable is modern breast imaging in differentiating benign from malignant breast lesions in the symptomatic population?. *Clin Radiol.* 1999; 54:676–682.
 10. Tiwari P, Ghosh S, Agrawal VK. Evaluation of breast lesions by digital mammography and ultrasound along with fine-needle aspiration cytology correlation. *J Cancer Res Ther.* 2018; 14(5):1071-1074.
 11. Shetty MK, Shah YP, Sharman RS. Prospective evaluation of the value of combined mammographic and sonographic assessment in patients with palpable abnormalities of the breast. *J Ultrasound Med.* 2003; 22(3):263-270.
 12. Kumar AMS, Tanwar NS. Evaluation of breast lump using elastography, histopathology and its diagnostic accuracy. *Int Surg J* 2019; 6:574-80.
 13. Thomas R, Das SK, Balasubramanian G, Chandrappa A. Correlation of Mammography, Ultrasound and Sonoelastographic Findings with Histopathological Diagnosis in Breast Lesions. *Cureus.* 2022; 14(12):e32318.
 14. Chhadi S, Chhadi T, Bagde K. Ultrasound elastography evaluation of breast masses with FNAC and/or histopathological correlation. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2018; 6:4034-8.
 15. Sakalecha AK, Parameshwar KBH, Savagave SG, Naik BR. The Role of Ultrasonography and Elastography in Differentiating Benign From Malignant Breast Masses with Pathologic Correlation. *Journal of Diagnostic Medical Sonography.* 2022; 38(3):226-234.
 16. Menezes R, Sardesai S, Furtado R, Sardesai M. Correlation of Strain Elastography with Conventional Sonography and FNAC/Biopsy. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2016; 10(7):TC05-TC10.
 17. Bojanic K, Katavic N, Smolic M, et al. Implementation of Elastography Score and Strain Ratio in Combination with B-Mode Ultrasound Avoids Unnecessary Biopsies of Breast Lesions. *Ultrasound Med Biol.* 2017; 43(4):804-816.